

Bandwidth enhancement of millimeter-wave microstrip patch antenna array for 5G mobile communication networks

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposed enhancing the bandwidth of a millimeter wave microstrip patch antenna (MPA) and its array for a 5G mobile communication network. The proposed antenna is designed and fabricated on a Rogers RT Duroid 5,880 substrate with a standard thickness of 0.5 mm, a relative dielectric constant of 2.2, and a tangent loss of 0.0009. With a center frequency of 28 GHz, a measured return loss of -21.37 dB, a bandwidth of 1.14 GHz, and a gain of 6.27 dBi, the proposed single element operates in the local multipoint distribution service band. The proposed antenna is designed and manufactured as an array of 1×2 and 1×4 elements. The 2-element MPA array has a measured bandwidth of 1.207 GHz and a gain of 7.76 dBi, higher than that of a single element. The 4-element MPA array achieved a measured bandwidth of 2.685 GHz and a gain of 9.87 dBi, which is higher than the 2-element and single-element arrays at 28 GHz. This demonstrates that the array of antennas improves gain and bandwidth significantly. Hence, the proposed antenna and array are suitable for 5G mobile communication networks due to their small size.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The requirement for extremely high throughput and more effective communication technology has already resulted in a significant expansion of wireless communication over time. When comparing fifth-generation (5G) base stations to their fourth-generation (4G) counterparts, for example, mobile devices require higher bandwidth [1]. Improved antenna systems are needed to meet the flexibility standards of designs, high gain, and enhanced bandwidth of operation for 5G [1], [2]. Since 5G communications require higher bandwidth, many frequency bands, including 28 GHz, 38 GHz, V band, and E band (71-76 GHz, 81-86 GHz, and 91-93 GHz), can be utilized [3].

A new age of technical development is being ushered in by 5G. The need for communication is shifting globally, and 5G has the potential to revolutionize civilization. It can be used for applications in autonomous driving, robotics, aviation, and the medical field owing to its data transmission rates of more than 1 Gbps [4], [5]. The pioneering spectrum bands for the 5G deployment have been identified as 680 MHz, 3.5 GHz, and 26/28 GHz [5]. To that end, many techniques that can enable 5G communication have been proposed in the literature. The slots technique, antenna array technique, defective ground plane structure, and metamaterial have all been applied to enhance performance parameters to satisfy the demands of 5G technology [6]–[8]. The millimeter-wave (mm-Wave) antenna is an important element of the 5G

communication system microstrip antennas have been widely used to date due to their advantages of being compact, lightweight, and simple to integrate which are a good fit for usage in a range of wireless applications, including those for aviation, satellite communication, missiles, and medical applications [9]–[13]. Moreover, it comes with the disadvantage of lower bandwidth which can be enhanced utilizing various designed methods [14], [15] and losses caused by the surface wave; numerous works have been performed to utilize it. Even so, these techniques significantly increase complexity and cost [16]. Similarly, for mm-wave 5G applications, several printed antennas were proposed employing various techniques [17]–[20]. The feeding technique is one of the significant characteristics used to increase impedance bandwidth. However, the feeding method varies depending on antenna fabrication, price, and working mechanism with additional radiation, together with impedance matching [21].

Recently, most researchers presented various antenna design techniques for 5G applications. Antenna arrays designed for the mm-wave band were implemented on mobile handsets, but their structures all seem to be three-dimensional, creating incorporation challenges [22]–[24]. Array antennas, such as patch, slot, Vivaldi, and quasi-Yagi antennas were designed in a variety of configurations in [25]–[28]. Aghoutane *et al.* [12] proposed a broadband square slotted 2×1 slotted patch antenna array for 5G cell phone applications at 30 GHz. Similarly, Hasnaoui and Mazri [1] designed and simulated a rectangular patch array antenna for mm-wave applications. Likewise, Zafar *et al.* [4] proposed a spherical beam steering antenna design for next-generation mobile devices. According to Sohail *et al.* [29], an array of 1×4 antennas are presented utilizing Rogers RT/duroid5880 material, the results of the proposed arrays obtained indicate that the linear array has greater gain than the planar array, however, the planar array has superior bandwidth and return loss. Bangash *et al.* [30] proposed a patch antenna array for mm-wave applications.

Following this trend, to support 5G wireless communication, this paper proposes using a variant of the microstrip patch antenna (MPA) array at 28 GHz. With improved bandwidth and gain. The proposed MPA array would be capable of handling high data bit rates and high-frequency spectrum speeds.

2. ANTENNA DESIGN METHOD

The antenna employs Rogers RT 5,880 with $\epsilon_r=2.2$, $\tan \delta=0.0009$ and thickness, $h=0.5$ mm. As shown in Figure 1(a), the MPA employs a slit square-shaped antenna with a transmission line. The antenna was designed and fabricated at 28 GHz. The array is used to improve the bandwidth and gain of the proposed antenna. The designed array has been completed using an array approach as shown in Figure 1(b) and (c) array of 1×2 and 1×4 elements a microstrip feeding method is used for the design antennas. The fabricated prototype of the single-element, an array of 1×2 and 1×4 of the proposed antenna is shown in Figures 1(d)-(f) respectively. Theoretical calculations are used to determine the actual size of the rectangular patch antenna. In (1)–(4) of the transmission and cavity model of the MPA are used in the design of the antenna [31]–[33].

Specifically, the patch length is below $\lambda/2$ in order to allow the fundamental TM_{10} mode. Where λ is the wavelength expressed as $\lambda_0/\sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}}$ and λ_0 which demonstrates free space wavelength while ϵ_{eff} indicates effective dielectric substrate. The length and width of the patch are increased on each end by a distance ΔL , expressed as (1):

$$\Delta L = 0.412h \frac{(E_{eff}+0.3)\left(\frac{W}{h}+0.264\right)}{(E_{eff}-0.264)\left(\frac{W}{h}+0.8\right)} \quad (1)$$

Where h expressed the thickness of the substrate and W indicates the patch width. The patch effective length, L_{eff} is expressed as (2):

$$L_{eff} = L + 2\Delta L \quad (2)$$

Where L represents the patch length. Moreover, for a resonance frequency, f_0 the patch effective length is expressed as (3):

$$L_{eff} = \frac{c}{2f_0\sqrt{E_{eff}}} \quad (3)$$

Likewise, patch width antenna is expressed as (4):

$$W = \frac{c}{2f_0\sqrt{\frac{E_r+1}{2}}} \quad (4)$$

where $c=3\times 10^8$ m/s is the speed of light.

Figure 1. Design and prototype of the proposed MPA at 28 GHz (a) single element MPA, (b) MPA array of 1×2 elements, substrate size is 10.3×14.2 mm, (c) MPA array of 1×4 elements, substrate size is 14.3×26.2 mm, (d) prototype of single element, (e) prototype of 1×2 elements, and (f) prototype of 1×4 elements

The dimensions of the MPA are substrate width=7.24 mm, substrate length=6.3 mm, patch width=4 mm, patch length=3.3 mm, substrate thickness=0.5 mm, patch thickness=0.035 mm, feed length=3.1 mm, feed width=0.8 mm, slit width=0.1 mm, slit length=2.95 mm.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed antenna array was modeled using CST microwave studio. The simulation was validated by comparing the results obtained after fabrication to the measured results. The parameters under consideration are reflection coefficient, surface current distribution, radiation pattern and gain.

3.1. Single element MPA

The simulated and measured reflection S_{11} of the single element MPA at 28 GHz is shown in Figure 2. According to the figure, the proposed antenna operates at 28 GHz and has a simulated reflection coefficient (S_{11}) of -23.7 dB. The resonant frequency of the fabricated antenna is measured at 27.5 GHz with S_{11} of -21.37 dB and a bandwidth of 1.14 GHz that ranges from 26.96 GHz to 28.1 GHz. The difference between measured and simulated resonant frequencies can be attributed to fabrication tolerances and cable losses. Likewise, the radiation patterns of the single-element MPA have been simulated at 28 GHz. Figure 3 shows the radiations patterns of the single-element MPA in the E-plane and H-plane at 28 GHz. From Figure 3(a), it can be observed that the radiation patterns at the resonant frequency of 28 GHz in directional in the E-plane and omnidirectional in the H-plane as shown in Figure 3(b). Furthermore, Figure 4 depicts the surface current distribution of the single-element MPA at 28 GHz. It can be seen that at 28 GHz, the maximum surface current is directed around the edges of the patch, feedline and vertical slit. However, the antenna achieved a high gain of 6.27 dBi.

3.2. MPA array of 1×2 elements

Figure 5 shows the simulated and measured S_{11} for 2-element array MPA, showing above 28 GHz with simulated S_{11} of -31.07 dB. The resonant frequency of the fabricated antenna is measured at 28.5 GHz with S_{11} of -22.37 dB and a bandwidth of 1.207 GHz that ranges between 27.84 GHz to 29.05 GHz. This demonstrates that the bandwidth of the 2-element MPA array exceeds that of the single element throughout the frequency range. The gain with a 1×2 MPA array is 7.76 dBi, which is a gain increase of 1.51 dBi. Furthermore, the radiation patterns of the single-element MPA have also been simulated. Figure 6 depicts the radiation patterns of a 2-element MPA array in the E-plane and H-plane at 28 GHz. The radiation patterns at the resonant frequency of 28 GHz are directional in the E-plane as shown in Figure 6(a) and omnidirectional

in the H-plane as shown in Figure 6(b). This demonstrates an increased bandwidth and gain over the single-element MPA. Moreover, Figure 7 depicts the surface current distribution of the proposed 1×2 MPA array at 28 GHz. It can be seen that at 28 GHz, the maximum surface current is directed around the edges of the patch, feedline and vertical slit.

Figure 2. Simulated and measured S_{11} of the single element MPA

Figure 3. Radiation patterns of the single element MPA (a) E-plane and (b) H-plane

Figure 4. Surface current distribution of the single element MPA

Figure 5. Simulated and measured S_{11} of the MPA array of 1×2 elements

Figure 6. Radiation patterns of the MPA array of 1×2 elements (a) E-plane and (b) H-plane

Figure 7. Surface current distribution of the MPA of 1×2 elements

3.3. MPA array of 1×4 elements

Figure 8 shows a comparison of simulated and measured reflection coefficients for the 4-element array MPA, the proposed antenna resonates at 28 GHz and with a simulated S_{11} of -30.71 dB. The fabricated antenna has a resonant frequency of 27.8 GHz, with a measured S_{11} of -19.37 dB, and a bandwidth of 2.685 GHz, which ranges between 26.66 GHz and 29.35 GHz. At 28 GHz, the bandwidth of the 4-element MPA array is greater than that of the 2-element and single-element MPA arrays. The single-element MPA has a gain of 6.27 dBi and the 2-element MPA array has a gain of 7.76 dBi. The gain with a 1×4 MPA array is 9.87 dBi, which is a 2.11 dBi increase over a 1×2 MPA array. Furthermore, the radiation patterns of the single-element MPA have also been simulated. Figure 9 depicts the radiation patterns of a 4-element MPA array in the E-plane and H-plane at 28 GHz. It is observed that the radiation patterns at the resonant

frequency of 28 GHz are directional in the E-plane as shown in Figure 9(a) and omnidirectional in the H-plane as shown in Figure 9(b). Similarly, this design has demonstrated an increased bandwidth and gain over the single-element MPA and 12 MPA arrays. As a result, when compared to the 2-element patch antenna and the single patch antenna, the directivity and gain are significantly increased. Moreover, Figure 10 depicts the surface current distribution of the proposed 1×4 MPA array at 28 GHz. It can be seen that at 28 GHz. This demonstrates the suitability of this antenna design for use in 5G applications.

Figure 8. Simulated and measured S_{11} of the MPA array of 1×4 elements

Figure 9. Radiation patterns of the MPA array of 1×4 elements (a) E-plane and (b) H-plane

Figure 10. Surface current distribution of the MPA of 1×4 elements

In addition, Table 1 summarizes the measured bandwidth and directivity values at 28 GHz for the MPA 1, 2, and 4 rectangular parallel feed arrays. According to the table, increasing the number of elements increases gain, bandwidth and directivity implying that the four-element patch antenna has high

characteristics. When the results were compared to the previous work, which is illustrated in Table 2, the following conclusions were reached: first, there is no fabrication or validation of their design between simulation and measurement. Second, the proposed array antenna achieves better results in terms of bandwidth, reflection coefficient and directivity; and finally, the measured values obtained are comparable to those obtained at 28 GHz and provide high bandwidth (2.685 GHz).

Table 1. Summary results of single element, 1×2 and 1×4 array MPA

Antenna design	Measured S_{11} (dB)	Measured bandwidth (GHz)	Directivity (dBi)
Single element	-21.37	1.14	6.27
1×2 MPA	-22.37	1.207	7.76
1×4 MPA	-19.37	2.685	9.87

Table 2. Comparison with previous work of different 1×4 array MPA

Ref	Resonance frequency (GHz)	S_{11} (dB)	Bandwidth (GHz)	Directivity (dBi)
[29]	28.00	-16.66	0.94	10.00
[30]	27.09	-42.6	1.63	10.95
[1]	28.00	-35.6	2.2	12.87
[4]	28.00	-17.00	-	6.9214
This work	28.00	-30.71	2.685	9.87

4. CONCLUSION

MPA with increased performance in terms of speed, size, data rate, and efficiency are required for mm-wave applications. As a result, enhancement methods are required. This study proposes a new antenna array design for the 5G mobile communication network at 28 GHz. A four-element antenna array's bandwidth and directivity increased when compared to single-element and two-element array antennas, as demonstrated by the simulated and measured results comparison. The 5G antenna and array can be used for future 5G mobile communications due to their compactness and small size.

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